

THE NEED TO CREATE A CULTURE OF HEALTHY LIFE IN YOUTH

Z. Sh. Boymurodov

(Uzbekistan, Karshi State University)

Annotation.: The article is devoted to defining the theoretical and methodological foundations of lifestyle research. For this, first of all, it is necessary to carry out a theoretical explanation of the "lifestyle" category, that is, to reveal the relationship between the content and structural elements of the concept. Also, in order to study the specific aspects of human lifestyle from a scientific standpoint, it is necessary to analyze it not only in a static state, but also in a dynamic state. Relying on these two theoretical approaches used in all lifestyle studies, revealing the lifestyle as a concept that expresses a specific form of human individual or collective life activity, determining the structural structure of the lifestyle, expressing the main properties of the elements included in this composition, and revealing the forms of the lifestyle according to the character ; the issue of showing the factors that cause the emergence of positive and negative lifestyles has been studied.

Key words: lifestyle, explanation, trend, free time, participation in community affairs, labor activity, habit, skill, healthy lifestyle.

In order to give a favorable tone to the lifestyle of young people, it is necessary to establish healthy habits and skills in them. It is impossible to give a rational touch to the marriage of young men and women without getting them used to regularly perform actions that increase the effectiveness of their lives and activities. The importance of this social task is especially great today, when harmful habits are increasing more and more, a whole industry promoting them is taking root, and young people are imitating them.

Healthy habits and skills mean actions that serve to increase the effectiveness of human life and activity and are formed by long-term repetition.

There is no strictly accepted classification of these habits and skills. However, the main ones can be listed. In particular, they include:

- Much has been said about the fact that physical activity keeps not only the human body, but also the mind healthy - there is no need to repeat it. However, it should be noted that physical activity means not only physical training and sports, but also the habit of being in constant motion;

- healthy nutrition ensures the stability of human physical capabilities and activities in life, thereby increasing life expectancy and quality of life; in some cases, a healthy diet can protect a person from various diseases and strengthen his health;

- reasonable agenda means correct allocation of time budget; the rational organization of work and non-work time, the correct determination of the time required for daily tasks gives an optimal tone to the lifestyle, in addition, this habit ensures that a person's life goes smoothly;

- the habit of striving for positivity is also important - it subordinates human actions to good goals, gives an optimistic tone to his psyche; a strong source that ensures that a person's life does not go off track in the anxious, problem-filled periods of life is also related to the habit of striving for positivity;

- politeness is one of the factors that develop interpersonal relations; while a person lives in society, he is obliged to regularly communicate with people like him in order to achieve his goals; if politeness does not become a habit, such communication will not be effective and will not arouse the goodwill of others;

- the habit of healthy thinking occurs on the basis of mastering the laws of logic, relying on life experience in reasoning, subordinating one's thoughts to moral norms; such thinking allows a person to understand his interests more deeply, to take into account the interests of others.

Healthy habits and skills are important in young people's lives. He subordinates the marriage of young men and women to the criteria of rationality. On the other hand, healthy habits are recognized as one of the important determinants

of sustainable social development. For this reason, in developed countries, great attention is paid to strengthening people's healthy habits and skills.

For example, in Singapore, a healthy lifestyle campaign is being implemented, which includes more than 40 national programs. It is commendable that these programs include grants aimed at building healthy habits and skills. In the Philippines, since 2003, the "National Healthy Lifestyle Campaign" has been held. Its main purpose is related to the formation of a conscious attitude to health in people. A similar campaign has been launched in Argentina. It focuses on the issues of increasing physical activity of citizens, organizing a healthy diet and getting rid of harmful habits. In particular, the "Argentina in Action" program dedicated to the promotion of physical activity is being actively implemented. In Israel, activities in this direction are carried out, on the one hand, within the framework of the nationwide "Health School" program, and on the other hand, within the framework of the city-level "Active and Healthy City" program.

It is not for nothing that attention is paid to these programs at the national level. The fact is that healthy habits and skills are not a phenomenon that is formed spontaneously. Its emergence and development depends on a number of factors. Among these factors, the social environment has a special place. Social environment - a set of socio-economic, political and spiritual conditions under which a person lives and works - is the most powerful source of motivation for the formation of healthy habits and skills. In an environment where physical activity, a healthy diet, a reasonable daily routine, the pursuit of positivity, politeness, healthy thinking are valued and glorified, members of society turn these habits and skills into the basis of their lifestyle. In a social environment where healthy habits and skills are not valued, it is very difficult to find them.

But healthy habits and skills are not created under the influence of social environment. There are also personal factors that set the stage for it. For example, the formation of healthy habits is related to a person's financial capabilities. Because, let's say, physical activity, healthy eating requires having a certain amount of money.

Material opportunities also affect a person's mentality and way of thinking. As a person's material condition improves, the possibilities of establishing healthy habits also expand. Physical activity, healthy eating, reasonable daily routine, striving for positivity, politeness, and healthy thinking are left as a wish in conditions of limited financial opportunities.

There is also a certain relationship between healthy habits and skills and the level of upbringing of a person. Because the habits related to healthy thinking are mental education, the habits related to physical activity are physical education, the habits related to politeness are moral education, the habits related to work are labor education, and the habits related to showing activity in community affairs are determined as a result of patriotic education. As the level of education of a person increases, so do the healthy habits included in his lifestyle. An uneducated person cannot have healthy habits and skills, because, as we mentioned above, such habits and skills are not formed spontaneously.

References

1. Majidov M.A. Socio-philosophical problems of human personality transformation in postmodern society: Fals.f. on fals.d. diss. autoref.- Samarkand: SamDU, 2021.
2. Marcel G. Byt i imet.- Novocherkassk: Saguna, 1994.
3. Masuda Yo. Information society and postindustrial society. - M.: AST, 1983.
4. Melnikov A. E. K voprosu o ponyatii finansovogo mechanism.// Upravlenie ekonomicheskimi sistemami. Electronic scientific journal, 2017, No. 7.
5. Merzlyakov A.A. Grazhdanskoe sotsialnoe uchastie kak universalnaya tekhnologiya sotsialnogo upravleniya (na materialakh razrabotki i realizatsii gradostroitelnyx proektov): Autoref. dis. ... candy. social. nauk.- M., 2007.- B.74.